

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Acceptance Note for

TEBT-2025-0014

Submission Title	ToxTempAssistant: Using Large Language Models to Standardise Cell-Based Toxicity Test Method Descriptions
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0014
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley 0000-0003-4021-0785 ▾
Editor Declaration of Interests	The editor is not aware of any conflicts of interest that could compromise the handling of this submission.
Number of Reviewers	1 editor and 3 peer-reviewers
Submission Type	Research Article ▾
Preregistration Level	N/A (Not Applicable) ▾ (explanation)
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17192970
Report Number	3 ▾
Evaluation Stage	Peer-Review ▾
Evaluation Date	12 Feb 2026
Use of AI in evaluation	DataSeer.ai was used to perform data availability checks on the manuscript.
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript evaluates the performance of three untuned Large Language Models (LLMs) for summarising information about toxicological assays according to OECD reporting requirements, as they are specified in the ToxTemp assay reporting template. This is important work because complying with standardised reporting requirements is challenging for researchers to accomplish, but is fundamental to making research data more readily reusable. Computer-in-the-loop processes that reduce the amount of effort and error in completing such checklists could contribute to their improved uptake and impact. LLMs may help with this, but tuning LLMs is expensive, so understanding how well an untuned LLM might perform is valuable.

Editorial triage did not identify any issues likely to compromise the effectiveness of the peer-review process. The peer-reviewers responded very positively to the manuscript and engaged deeply with the work, making a large number of wide-ranging comments. On the whole, these were related to clarifying the methods and more clearly contextualising the findings and conclusions of the study. In my opinion, the revisions to the manuscript made by the authors appropriately responded to the reviewers' comments. I also checked back with the reviewer who made the most detailed comments if the authors' clarifications had revealed any issues with their methods. This reviewer stated they were satisfied with the revisions. I am therefore pleased to accept this manuscript for publication.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 1 round of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 1 round of peer-review.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17278785>